

SOME REACTIONS WITH 2-PROPIONYL- α -NAPHTHOL

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Action of sulphur dichloride, thionyl chloride, and sulphuryl chloride on 2-propionyl- α -naphthol has been investigated. Action of chlorine, bromine, nitric acid and diazobenzene chloride on the reaction products has also been studied.

The reactions between benzene and naphthalene derivatives and the chlorides of sulphur viz., sulphur monochloride, sulphur dichloride, thionyl chloride and sulphuryl chloride have been studied by various workers. Recently sulphides of the general formula, R-S-R (where R represents COCH_3 , OH, C_{10}H_7 ; OH, C_{10}H_7 ; OH, COOH , C_{10}H_7 ; etc.) have been obtained by Airan and Shah (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1940, 9, III, 115).

In the present investigation 2-propionyl- α -naphthol was allowed to react with sulphur dichloride, thionyl chloride and sulphuryl chloride separately using bismuth chloride as a catalyst. It was also considered of interest to see how the reagents like nitric acid and chlorine would react with this naphthol derivative.

Thionyl chloride was allowed to react at 60° as well as at room temperature with 2-propionyl- α -naphthol with the same catalyst in different media (acetic acid, benzene, and ether), but in all cases the original compound was obtained.

The sulphide on treatment with bromine gives a bromo compound, identical with 4-bromo-2-propionyl- α -naphthol (Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3097). Thus the position of the sulphur linkage is the same as that of bromine. A chloro compound (m. p. 93°) was obtained by the action of chlorine on the sulphide and it is identical with the chloro compound obtained by the action of sulphuryl chloride or chlorine on 2-propionyl- α -naphthol. Evidently the sulphide linkage is broken by chlorine and the compound is 4-chloro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.

Similarly the nitro compound obtained from 2-propionyl- α -naphthol by analogy with the above bromo and chloro compounds has been given the structure as 4-nitro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.

The following conclusions are arrived at :

- (1) 2-Propionyl- α -naphthol does not react with thionyl chloride.
- (2) 2-Propionyl- α -naphthol reacts with sulphur dichloride to give 4: 4'-dihydroxy-3: 3'-dipropionyl-dinaphthyl trisulphide.
- (3) The sulphide obtained is stable towards sulphuryl chloride and acetic anhydride.
- (4) The sulphur linkage is broken by chlorine, bromine, nitric acid and diazobenzene chloride yielding respectively 4-chloro-, 4-bromo-, 4-nitro- and 4-benzeneazo-2-propionyl- α -naphthols.
- (5) The sulphide parts with two atoms of sulphur during the process of benzylation.
- (6) 2-Propionyl- α -naphthol reacts with sulphuryl chloride, nitric acid and chlorine to give 4-chloro-, 4-nitro- and 4-chloro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol respectively.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

(1) 4: 4'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dipropionyl-dinaphthyl Trisulphide.—To a solution of 2-propionyl- α -naphthol (5 g.) in ether at room temperature was added sulphur dichloride (2 c.c.) using bismuth chloride as a catalyst. Within half an hour a yellow solid separated. It was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 190°. It gave the ferric chloride reaction for the hydroxy group. (Found: S, 19.9. $C_{28}H_{22}O_4S_3$ requires S, 19.45 per cent).

The above sulphide was refluxed with acetic anhydride on a sand-bath for 8 hours and then poured in ice-cold water. The compound on crystallisation from alcohol was found to be identical with the original sulphide. Thus no acetylation of the sulphide could take place.

The sulphide was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution and benzoyl chloride was added drop by drop. The white compound obtained was washed with sodium hydroxide and then with water. It was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 202°. It contained sulphur. (Found: S, 5.21. $C_{40}H_{30}O_6S$ requires S, 5.01 per cent). Its molecular weight was determined by refluxing a known quantity of the benzoyl derivative with a known excess of potassium hydroxide, the excess of which was then back titrated against standard hydrochloric acid. (Found: M. W., 628.8. $C_{40}H_{30}O_6S$ requires M. W., 638) Thus during the process of benzylation two atoms of sulphur are shed off.

The sulphide (2 g.) was taken in 25 c.c. of dry benzene. To this 5 c.c. of sulphuryl chloride were added with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed over a water-bath for about one hour at 60°. It was filtered off and the filtrate was distilled under reduced pressure. No new compound was obtained. The sulphide on the filter paper was identical with the original sulphide. The sulphur linkage is thus stable towards sulphuryl chloride.

4-Chloro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—To a solution of the sulphide (5 g.) in acetic acid dry chlorine was passed with constant shaking. Immediately a solid came out. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 93° and found to be identical with chloro compound obtained from 2-propionyl- α -naphthol by the action of sulphuryl chloride. It showed the absence of sulphur and the presence of the hydroxy group. (Found: Cl, 15.40. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.14 per cent). Chlorine, thus breaks the sulphur linkage.

4-Bromo-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—Compound (1) was suspended in acetic acid and bromine was added dropwise till the solid went into solution. A crystalline compound was obtained after half an hour, m. p. 98° and it showed the presence of bromine and the hydroxy group and the absence of sulphur. It showed the absence of bromine in the side-chain. (Found: Br, 29.11. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2Br$ requires Br, 28.67 per cent). Mixed melting point with the compound prepared according to the method of Hantzsch (*loc. cit.*) gave no depression.

4-Nitro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—To a solution of the sulphide (5 g.) in acetic acid (25 c.c.) nitric acid (d 1.42) diluted to 10 c.c. with acetic acid was added with constant shaking. After the reaction was over the whole reaction mixture was poured in water and the solid compound was removed and crystallised out of alcohol, m. p. 158°. It showed the presence of nitrogen and the hydroxy group and the absence of sulphur.

Thus the position of the nitro group was confirmed by the absence of sulphur. (Found: N, 6.07. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.71 per cent).

4-Benzeneazo-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—The sulphide was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution and ice-cold solution of diazobenzene chloride, prepared according to the method of Shah *et al.* (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1943, 11, V, 85), was added with constant shaking. A brown dye was obtained which showed the absence of sulphur and was identical with 5-benzeneazo-2-propionyl- α -naphthol, prepared according to Goldzweig and Keiser (*J. prakt. Chem.* ii, 43, 96). It melted at 110°.

(2) 4-Chloro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—To a solution of 2-propionyl- α -naphthol (4 g.) in ether was added sulphuryl chloride (3 c.c.) in the presence of bismuth chloride (catalyst). A vigorous reaction was started and within a couple of minutes a solid compound separated. It was crystallised from alcohol. It gave positive ferric chloride reaction and showed the absence of chlorine in the side-chain. (Found: Cl, 15.41. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.14 per cent).

To a solution of 2-propionyl- α -naphthol (5 g.) in acetic acid dry chlorine was passed with constant shaking. A solid came out which was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 93° and was found to be identical with the above compound (mixed m. p.). Its constitution is proved by its formation from the sulphide with known constitution.

(3) 4-Nitro-2-propionyl- α -naphthol.—2-Propionyl- α -naphthol (5 g.) taken with acetic acid (25 c.c.) in a conical flask and 3 c.c. of nitric acid (d 1.42) diluted to 10 c.c. with acetic acid was added to it. There was reaction in the cold with evolution of brown fumes. A yellow solid came out. It was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 158°. It contained hydroxy group and nitrogen. It was found to be identical with the above compound (No. 2) and gave no depression in the mixed melting point. Its constitution is proved by its formation from the sulphide of known constitution.

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